

03.06.2021

Newsletter

EDITORIAL

We are excited about the outcome of the first step towards a significant delivery of the project. We shall give the EC and our society an insight into the main areas of technology that are essential for delivering 5G and 6G solutions of the future. COREnect and its amazing team of nearly 100 experts have identified some technology areas within three Expert Groups.

You can read below the Editorial by Gerhard P. Fettweis, Vodafone Chair Professor, COREnect Project Coordinator, TU Dresden.

EDITORIAL

"Hardware Enabling Technologies for 6G Networks" workshop

Tuesday, 8 June 2021, 14:00-15:30/16:00-17:30 CEST

AGENDA

"Components and Hardware on the Road to 6G" panel

Thursday, 10 June, 11:30-13:00 CEST.

AGENDA

COREnect stakeholders

COREnect stakeholder pictures: The COREnect team revised the stakeholder pictures, building up upon the work from the deliverable D4.1 "Initial report on community building and outreach strategy". Many documents and reports were thoroughly analysed and the COREnect partners added their contributions, leading to two new stakeholder pictures, describing with more details the "COREnect provisioning ecosystem" and the "COREnect Use Case Ecosystem".

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6G White Paper: An interview with Carlos Jesús Bernardos Cano

COREnect's WP4 Leader Jacques Magen has interviewed Carlos Jesús Bernardos from University Carlos III of Madrid, who has just taken over as lead co-editor of this White Paper from his colleague Arturo Azcorra, who was the previous lead co-editor, along with Mikko Uusitalo from Nokia (who is also the project coordinator of the Hexa-X flagship project).

READ

“Pre-release” of D3.3 Initial COREnect industry roadmap

This document is a “pre-release” of the envisioned COREnect report D3.3 (Initial COREnect industry roadmap). As the draft version of D3.3 is still under construction, this pre-release has no ambition to be complete nor to represent the overall view of the COREnect consortium, its experts and/or its stakeholders.

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COREnect in the European 5G Annual Journal 2021

The European 5G Annual Journal 2021 has been released by 5GPPP. Check it out for an interesting read and to get an overview of the 5G PPP activities and the COREnect project (pag.89).

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COREnect permanent call for new experts

COREnect is opening a permanent invitation to female experts and experts from SMEs to join the EGs. The COREnect consortium intends with this to enrich the project with different background, perspectives, and viewpoint.

[APPLY](#)

COREnect
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